

Understanding between Riemann hypothesis and Orbitals of Atom

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December 15, 2023

Abstract

By utilizing the ergodicity provided between Riemann hypothesis and generalized prime number sequence, density-based probability orbitals in atom could be understood in concept of Virial theorem.

1 Introduction

There has been discussion on the understanding in Riemann hypothesis from the perspective of atom orbitals[1]. This paper would try an explanation of the relation by Virial theorem interpreted in concept of entropy.

2 Ergodicity

Ergodicity in prime number sequence as $x^3 + x^2$ could be given by any definition in extended generalized prime number sequence:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall p \in \mathbb{P}, b, b', b'', b''' \dots \in \mathbb{R} \Rightarrow p_{n+1} &= (x^3 + x^2) (bp_n + b'p_{k'} + b''p_{k''} + b'''p_{k'''} \dots) \dots \\ \implies x^3 + x^2 &= x^2(x+1) = \frac{p_{n+1}}{bp_n + b'p_{k'} + b''p_{k''} + b'''p_{k'''} \dots} > 1 \end{aligned}$$

This result has implication that any given division between two prime numbers forms ergodicity with function $x^3 + x^2$ in quotient plane.

3 Revisiting Virial Theorem in Entropy

Virial theorem is about kinetic energy of a stable system of discrete particle[3]. For state equation based on Virial theorem[2]:

$$Z \equiv \frac{P}{RT\rho} = A + B\rho + C\rho^2 + \dots$$

In Virial theorem based state equation, pressure P is sum of a power series by density ρ . This equation implies that any given entropy under temperature T in pressure P is another expression of density ρ that has concentration rate in overall ensemble.

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4 Riemann hypothesis: Translation to Radial Axis

In extension to upper ergodicity discussion:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} &= \prod_{p \text{ prime}} \frac{p^s - 1}{p^s} = \frac{p_1^s - 1}{p_1^s} \cdot \frac{p_2^s - 1}{p_2^s} \cdot \frac{p_3^s - 1}{p_3^s} \cdot \frac{p_4^s - 1}{p_4^s} \cdot \frac{p_5^s - 1}{p_5^s} \dots \\
 &= \frac{(\text{Composite} \in \mathbb{N})}{c_1^s} \cdot \frac{(\text{Composite} \in \mathbb{N})}{c_2^s} \cdot \frac{(\text{Composite} \in \mathbb{N})}{c_3^s} \cdot \frac{(\text{Composite} \in \mathbb{N})}{c_4^s} \dots \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{x^3 + x^2} \leq 1 \\
 &\implies \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} - \frac{1}{x^3 + x^2} \leq 0
 \end{aligned}$$

5 Translation in Radial Form

Assuming that $r = (a + bi)^3 + (a + bi)^2$ as position of entropy inside atom, entropy function could be put in ergodic form:

$$\text{s.t. } \frac{\pi^2 r^2}{(\sin \pi r)^2} \leq 1 \implies 0 \leq \left(1 - \frac{\pi^2 r^2}{(\sin \pi r)^2} \right)$$

And again, assuming 1 as dimensional representation in ζ function with power number m (e.g. in which upper 2) as correspond :

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\zeta(r^n)} - \frac{\pi^m r^m}{(\sin \pi r)^m}$$

which plots contour fractals as follows in Figure 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 in Appendix:

When $n = 2$ and $m = 2$ or 3 (Figure 1), represents a star shape with 6 small branches and 6 long branches in fractal with value of infinite.

When $n = 3$ and $m = 2$ or 3 (Figure 2), represents a star shape with 6 small branches, 3 longer, and 3 longest branches in fractal with value of infinite.

When $n = 4$ and $m = 2$ or 3 (Figure 3), represents a star shape with 12 small branches and 6 long branches with value of infinite.

When $n = 5$ and $m = 2$ or 3 (Figure 4), represents a star shape with 12 shortest branches with 3 longest branches and 3 shorter branches with value of infinite.

When $n = 6$ and $m = 2$ or 3 (Figure 5), represents a star shape with 18 shortest branches with 6 longest branches with value of infinite.

When $n = 7$ and $m = 2$ or 3 (Figure 6), represents a star shape with 18 shortest branches with 3 longest branches and 3 shorter branches with value of infinite.

6 Conclusion

Any probabilistic distribution of entropy given in atom could be expressed in ergodic form originated from Riemann hypothesis, in extension to Virial equation in state equation.

References

- [1] Johnathan P Keating. *Periodic orbits, spectral statistics, and the Riemann zeros*. Springer, 1999.
- [2] Robert J Silbey et al. *Physical chemistry*. John Wiley & Sons, 2022.
- [3] Wikipedia. *Virial theorem* — *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. <http://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Virial%20theorem&oldid=1188996716>. [Online; accessed 13-December-2023]. 2023.

7 Appendix

$n = 2, m = 2$

$n = 2, m = 3$

Table 1: In case of $n = 2$

$n = 3, m = 2$

$n = 3, m = 3$

Table 2: In case of $n = 3$

$$n = 4, m = 2$$

$$n = 4, m = 3$$

Table 3: In case of $n = 4$

$$n = 5, m = 2$$

$$n = 5, m = 3$$

Table 4: In case of $n = 5$

$$n = 6, m = 2$$

$$n = 6, m = 3$$

Table 5: In case of $n = 6$

$$n = 7, m = 2$$

$$n = 7, m = 3$$

Table 6: In case of $n = 7$